

ANTI-PATERSNS CATALOG IN C AND PYTHON

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA						
ID	TITLE					
G1	Lack of indentation					
EXAMPLES:						
(C)			(Python)			
<pre> 1 #include <stdio.h> 2 int main(){ 3 int a; 4 scanf("%d",&a); 5 printf("%d",&a); 6 return 0; 7 </pre>						
ERROR TYPE:	X (P)	Syntax		Semantics	X (C)	Style
CONTENT:	- General					
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C		X	Python	
PROBLEM:						
<p><u>C</u> - Lack of indentation is not exactly an error when using C language but highly recommended in any language to give readability to code.</p> <p><u>Python</u> - Indentation is required in the Python language. Lack of it causes the program not to run.</p>						
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:						
EVENTS						
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>						
EVENT 1 – C						
Student Id: 1781		Total of submissions of the exercise:			2	
The exercise that was being solved:						
Exercise 1.1						
Error			Fixed Error			

```

1 #include <stdio.h>
2 int main(){
3 int a;
4 scanf("%d",&a);
5 printf("%d",&a);
6 return 0;
7 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: Lack of indentation is a bad programming practice that will compromise code readability.

Fixed on submission:

Observation: The indentation has not been corrected.

EVENT 2 – C

Student Id: 5554

Total of submissions of the exercise:

4

The exercise that was being solved:

Exercise 1.1

Error

```

1 #include <stdio.h>
2 int main ()
3 {
4 int num;
5 printf ("Digite um numero inteiro: ");
6 scanf ("%d", &num);
7 printf ("O numero digitado foi: %d\n", num);
8
9 return 0;
10
11 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: Lack of indentation is a bad programming practice that will cause code viewing to be compromised.

Fixed Error

Fixed on submission:

Observation: The indentation has not been corrected.

EVENT 3 – C

Student Id: 4930

Total of submissions of the exercise:

10

The exercise that was being solved:

Exercise 2.1

Error

```

1 #include <stdio.h>
2 int primeiraFuncao(int a, int b){
3 if (a>b){
4 printf ("%d\n", a);}
5 else{
6 printf ("%d\n", b);
7 }
8 }
9 int main(){
10 }

```

Occurred in submission: 1

Fixed Error

```

1 #include <stdio.h>
2 int primeiraFuncao(int a, int b){
3
4 }
5 int main(int argc, char * argv){
6 int oi;
7 for(oi=1;oi<=argc; oi++){
8 printf ("%s\n", argv[oi]);
9 }
10 if (a>b){
11 printf ("%d\n", a);}
12 else{
13 printf ("%d\n", b);
14 }
15 }

```

Fixed on submission: 4

Observation: Lack of indentation is a bad programming practice that will cause code viewing to be compromised.

Observation: In the 4th submission the student indented part of the code and was improving during the following submissions.

EVENT 4 – C

Student Id: 2040

Total of submissions of the exercise:

4

The exercise that was being solved:

Exercise 4.1

Error

```
1 #include <stdio.h>
2
3 int soma(a,b)
4 {
5     int s;
6     s = a+b;
7
8     return(s);
9
10 }
11
12 float media(int a,int b)
13 {
14     float m;
15
16     m = (a+b)/(2.0);
17
18     return(m);
19 }
20
21 int main()
22 {
23     int a,b;
24     scanf("%d %d",&a,&b);
25     printf("%d ",soma(a,b));
26     printf("%.1f",media(a,b));
27     return(0);
28
29
30 }
```

Fixed Error

Occurred in submission: 1

Observation: Lack of indentation is a bad programming practice that will cause code viewing to be compromised.

Fixed on submission:

Observation: The indentation has not been corrected.

EVENT 1 – Python

Student Id: 4666

Total of submissions of the exercise:

12

The exercise that was being solved:

Exercise 1.1

Error

```
def main():
n = int(input())
print(n)
main()
```

Fixed Error

```
n = int(input())
print(n)
```

<p>Occurred in submission: 11 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 12 Observation: In reality, the student did not get the indentation, he solved the problem by removing the statement of the function that required indentation.</p>
EVENT 2 – Python	
<p>Student Id: 2635</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 7</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> n1 = int (input()) n2 = int (input()) if (n1>=n2) : print (n1, "n1") else : print (n2, "n2") </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> n1 = int (input()) n2 = int (input()) if (n1 >= n2) : print (n1, "n1") else : print (n2, "n2") </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 7 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3 – Python	
<p>Student Id: 4698</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 5</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> def main(): a = int(input()) b = int(input()) if a>b print(a) main() </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 2 Observation: Python requires indentation to work, even if it is only on one line, as is the case with the "print" line, it will not work.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> def main(): a = int(input()) b = int(input()) if a>b: print(a) else: print(b) main() </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4 – Python	
<p>Student Id: 4826</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 4</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> def media(a,b, self): media = (a + b)/2.0 return(media) </pre>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> def media(a,b): media = ((soma(a,b))/2.0) return(media) </pre>

Occurred in submission: 3

Observation: The "return" is not indented correctly.

Fixed on submission: 4

Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot

FOR STUDENTS

Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE
V1	Use of nonexistent variable

EXAMPLES:

<p>(C)</p> <pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em;"> 1 #include <stdio.h> 2 3 int main(void){ 4 int n; 5 6 scanf("%d", &n); 7 m = n; </pre>	
--	---

ERROR TYPE:	X	Syntax		Semantics		Style
CONTENT:	- Variable: declaration					
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C		X	Python	

PROBLEM:

C - When using an identifier, such as variable names, constants, structs, etc., it is necessary to tell the C language program what the identifier refers to. In the case of undeclared variables, the compiler will not be able to identify what that name is about in this scope.

Python - Python variable declaration is by assignment, which will define its data type. Using the variable before the assignment will generate an error.

CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:

- P_V2 – Use of reserved word for variable name
- V3 – Assignment using “==” instead of “=”

EVENTS

Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.

EVENT 1 – C

Student Id: 3430	Total of submissions of the exercise:	7
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The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 1.1

Error

```

3  int main(void){
4      int n;
5
6      scanf("%d", &n);
7      m = n;
8      printf("%d", &m);

```

Fixed Error

```

3  int main(void){
4      int n,m;
5
6      scanf("%d", &n);
7      m = n;
8      printf("%d", &m);

```

<p>Occurred in submission: 5 Observation: This error was made when the student was trying to solve another one (C_OF1).</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 6 Observation:</p>
EVENT 2 – C	
<p>Student Id: 4930</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 10</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 5 int main(int argc, char * argv){ 6 int oi; 7 for(oi=1;oi<=argc; oi++){ 8 printf("%s\n", argv[oi]); 9 } 10 if (a>b){ </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 4 Observation: Variables “a” and “b” were used from line 10, but they were not declared.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 5 int main(int argc, char * argv[]){ 6 int oi; 7 for(oi=1;oi<=argc; oi++){ 8 printf("%s\n", argv[oi]); 9 } 10 int a, b; 11 if (a>b){ </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3 – C	
<p>Student Id: 5098</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 12</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 1 # include <stdio.h> 2 int main () { 3 scanf("%d %d %d", &a, &b, &c); </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Variables “a”, “b,” and “c” were used from line 3, but they were not declared.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 1 # include <stdio.h> 2 int main () { 3 int a,b,c; 4 scanf("%d %d %d", &a, &b, &c); </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4 – C	
<p>Student Id: 1781</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 4</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre> 8 int media(int a,int b) 9 { 10 m = (a+b)/2; 11 return m; 12 } </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The variable “m” had not been declared.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre> 9 int media(int a,int b) 10 { 11 int m; 12 m = (a+b)/2; 13 return m; 14 } </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 1 – Python	
<p>Student Id: 2068</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 2</p>

The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1	
Error	Fixed Error
<pre>x = int (input()) print (a)</pre>	<pre>x = int (input()) print (x)</pre>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The variable "a" does not exist.	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 2 – Python	
Student Id: 4666	Total of submissions of the exercise: 12
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1	
Error	Fixed Error
<pre>def main () : n = int(input("Digite um numero que deseja: ")) print("O numero digitado e:",a)</pre>	<pre>def main () : n = int(input("Digite um numero que deseja: ")) print("O numero digitado e: ",n) main()</pre>
Occurred in submission: 5 Observation: The variable "a" does not exist.	Fixed on submission: 7 Observation:
EVENT 3 – Python	
Student Id: 5650	Total of submissions of the exercise: 10
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 8.1	
Error	Fixed Error
<pre>n= int(input()) c = 0 lista = [] while cont < n:</pre>	<pre>n= int(input()) c = 0 lista = [] while c < n:</pre>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The "cont" variable used in the "while" condition is nonexistent.	Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:
EVENT 4 – Python	
Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:
The exercise that was being solved:	
Error	Fixed Error
Occurred in submission: Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Groups working with step-by-step execution to understand errors – reinforce with exercises	
FOR STUDENTS	
Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE					
V3	Assignment using “==” instead of “=”					
EXAMPLES:						
(C)			(Python)			
5	 a == int(input("Digite um numero que deseja: "))					
ERROR TYPE:	X(P)	Syntax	X(C)	Semantics		Style
CONTENT:	- Variable: attribution					
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	X	Python		
PROBLEM:						
<p>C - The program will execute, but will not run properly, because the compiler understands the “==” as being used for comparison and not for assignment.</p> <p>Python - If “==” is used to first assign value to a variable, i.e., to declare it, it will cause a syntax error and the program will not execute. Otherwise, the program will execute, disregarding the assignment line with “==” because the compiler will understand that command as a comparison.</p>						
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RE2 – Use of “=” instead of “==” - V1 – Use of nonexistent variable - P_V2 – Use of reserved word for variable name 						
EVENTS						
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>						
EVENT 1 – C						
Student Id: 2950		Total of submissions of the exercise:			5	
The exercise that was being solved:						
Exercise 3.1						
Error			Fixed Error			
5	 soma = a+b+c;					
Occurred in submission: 3 Observation: The assignment is made with “=” not “==,” which is used in comparisons.			Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:			
EVENT 2 – C						
Student Id: 2936		Total of submissions of the exercise:			7	
The exercise that was being solved:						
Exercise 7.4						
Error			Fixed Error			

<pre>7 caractere == 0;</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 6 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: Observation: Uncorrected error. The student deleted line 7 where the error was and practically all the code for not being able to generate the expected result.</p>
EVENT 3 – C	
<p>Student Id: 2558 Total of submissions of the exercise: 3</p>	
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.2</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>7 n==(n*n);</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>7 n=(n*n);</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4 – C	
<p>Student Id: 1830 Total of submissions of the exercise: 5</p>	
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.2</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>6 res==1;</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>6 res=1;</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:</p>
EVENT 1 – Python	
<p>Student Id: 4666 Total of submissions of the exercise: 12</p>	
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>a == int(input("Digite um numero que deseja: "))</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 3 Observation: Used “==” instead of “=” to assign read value to the variable.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>n = int(input("Digite um numero que deseja: "))</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:</p>
EVENT 2 – Python	
<p>Student Id: 4978 Total of submissions of the exercise: 10</p>	
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.3</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>soma == soma + i</pre>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>soma = soma + i</pre>

Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:
EVENT 3 – Python	
Student Id: 4914	Total of submissions of the exercise: 2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.1	
Error <code>soma == a + b</code>	Fixed Error <code>s = a + b</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 4 – Python	
Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:
The exercise that was being solved:	
Error	Fixed Error
Occurred in submission: Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot	
FOR STUDENTS	
Introduce the error into a code and understand the consequences it generates	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE				
IF2	Missing quotes in the input function call				
EXAMPLES:					
	(C)		(Python)		
4	<code>scanf(%d, &n);</code>		<code>y = int(input("digite o segundo valor:))</code>		
ERROR TYPE:	X	Syntax		Semantics	Style
CONTENT:	- Data input function				
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C		X	Python
PROBLEM:					
<p><u>C</u> - The compiler does not understand what "%d" is and reports that "d" was not declared in the current scope. The program will not run.</p> <p><u>Python</u> - The text inside the parentheses following the "input" command is used to write a statement to the user about what the program expects them to type. This statement must be enclosed in double-quotes. Missing quotation marks will generate a syntax error causing the program not to run.</p>					
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_IF1 – Missing "&" in front of variable in "scanf" - C_IF6 – Missing “,” to separate first from second parameter in “scanf” - P_IF4 – Missing parentheses in “input” 					
EVENTS					
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>					
EVENT 1 – C					
Student Id: 2950		Total of submissions of the exercise:			2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1					
Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 2px 5px; margin-right: 5px;">4</div> <div style="color: red; font-family: monospace;">scanf(%d, &n);</div> </div>			Fixed Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 2px 5px; margin-right: 5px;">4</div> <div style="color: red; font-family: monospace;">scanf("%d", &n);</div> </div>		
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:			Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:		
EVENT 2 – C					
Student Id: 3529		Total of submissions of the exercise:			4
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1					
Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 2px 5px; margin-right: 5px;">5</div> <div style="color: red; font-family: monospace;">scanf(%d, &n);</div> </div>			Fixed Error <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; justify-content: center;"> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 2px 5px; margin-right: 5px;">5</div> <div style="font-family: monospace;">Attempt 1: scanf(%d, n);</div> </div>		

		Final: scanf("%d", &n);
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	5	Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:
EVENT 3 – C		
Student Id: 5226	Total of submissions of the exercise: 2	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 1.1		
Error		Fixed Error
4 scanf(%d,&a);		
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:		Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.
EVENT 4 – C		
Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:	
The exercise that was being solved:		
Error		Fixed Error
Occurred in submission: Observation:		Fixed on submission: Observation:
EVENT 1 – Python		
Student Id: 4762	Total of submissions of the exercise: 2	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1		
Error		Fixed Error
<pre>y = int(input("digite o segundo valor: "))</pre>		<pre>y = int(input("digite o segundo valor: "))</pre>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:		Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 2 – Python		
Student Id: 4786	Total of submissions of the exercise: 2	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1		
Error		Fixed Error
<pre>n = int(input("Digite o primeiro numero")) m = int(input("Digite o segundo numero"))</pre>		<pre>n = int(input("Digite o primeiro numero")) m = int(input("Digite o segundo numero"))</pre>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:		Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:

EVENT 3 – Python	
Student Id: 4730	Total of submissions of the exercise: 6
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.1	
Error	Fixed Error
<pre>a = int(input(Digite um numero inteiro: "))</pre>	<pre>a = int(input("Digite um numero inteiro: "))</pre>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Missing double quotation marks before the word "Digite" (type).	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 4 – Python	
Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:
The exercise that was being solved:	
Error	Fixed Error
Occurred in submission: Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot	
FOR STUDENTS	
Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE				
OF2	Missing quotes in output function				
EXAMPLES:					
(C)			(Python)		
5	<code>printf(%d, n);</code>		5	<code>print(Sim)</code>	
ERROR TYPE:					
		X	Syntax		Semantics
Style					
CONTENT: - Data output function					
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?					
		X	C		Python
PROBLEM:					
<p><u>C</u> - The compiler does not understand what "%d" is and reports that "d" was not declared in the current scope. The program will not run.</p> <p><u>Python</u> - When outputting a string, it must be enclosed in double quotation marks after the print command.</p>					
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_OF1 – Improper use of "&" in front of variable in "printf" - C_OF3 – Wrong spelling of "printf" command - C_OF5 – Parameter identifying incorrect or non-existent output data type - C_OF6 – Use of "&" instead of "%" in "printf" - OF4 – Missing comma to separate parameters in data output function - P_OF5 – "print" followed by "=" or other incorrect parameter 					
EVENTS					
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>					
EVENT 1 – C					
Student Id: 2950		Total of submissions of the exercise:			2
The exercise that was being solved:					
Exercise 1.1					
Error			Fixed Error		
5	<code>printf(%d, n);</code>		5	<code>printf("%d", n);</code>	
Occurred in submission: 1			Fixed on submission: 2		
Observation:			Observation:		
EVENT 2 – C					
Student Id: 1963		Total of submissions of the exercise:			2
The exercise that was being solved:					
Exercise 2.1					
Error			Fixed Error		
10	<code>prinfn("%d \n, n2);</code>		10	<code>printf("%d \n", n2);</code>	

Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 3 – C	
Student Id: 1830	Total of submissions of the exercise: 10
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.1	
Error	Fixed Error
18 <code>printf(%f)</code>	18 <code>printf("%d\n", s);</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The variable is missing to know the value to be printed, as well as other errors.	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 4 – C	
Student Id: 4922	Total of submissions of the exercise: 2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.2	
Error	Fixed Error
<pre> 5 6 7 8 9 10 if(n1 < n2){ printf(1); } else{ printf(0); } </pre>	<pre> 5 6 7 8 9 10 if(n1 < n2){ printf("1"); } else{ printf("0"); } </pre>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 1 – Python	
Student Id: 4826	Total of submissions of the exercise: 5
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1	
Error	Fixed Error
<pre> if a + b + c == 180: print(Sim) else: print(NAO) </pre>	<pre> if s == 180: print("Sim") else: print("NAO") </pre>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: Missing double quotation marks within the parentheses of the two "print" commands.	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 2 – Python	
Student Id: 4874	Total of submissions of the exercise: 6
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1	
Error	Fixed Error

```

if a + b + c == 180:
    print (Sim)
    print (a)
    print (b)
    print (c)
else:
    print (NAO)

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation: The words "Sim" and "NAO" within the "print" must be enclosed in quotation marks.

```

if a + b + c == 180:
    print ('Sim')
    print (a)
    print (b)
    print (c)
else:
    print ('NAO')

```

Fixed on submission: 4
Observation:

EVENT 3 – Python

Student Id: 3498 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 5

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.1

Error

```
print Sim
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```
print 'Sim'
```

Fixed on submission: 3
Observation:

EVENT 4 – Python

Student Id: 4682 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 3

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.1

Error

```
print (NAO)
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```
print ("NAO")
```

Fixed on submission: 3
Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot

FOR STUDENTS

Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE			
OF4	Missing comma to separate parameters in data output function			
EXAMPLES:				
(C)		(Python)		
16	<pre>printf("%d %d %d" a, b, c);</pre>	<pre>print ("Sim" a, b, c)</pre>		
ERROR TYPE:	X	Syntax	X	Semantics
CONTENT:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data output function - Function: passing parameter 			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	X	Python
PROBLEM:				
<p><u>C</u> - The compiler does not understand that the comma is missing and identifies this point as the end of the parameters of the output function, informing that it expected to find a ")".</p> <p><u>Python</u> - The compiler does not understand parameters that are not separated with a comma, causing the program not to run.</p>				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C_OF1 – Improper use of "&" in front of variable in "printf" - C_OF3 – Wrong spelling of "printf" command - OF2 – Missing quotes in output function - C_OF6 – Use of "&" instead of "%" in "printf" - C_OF5 – Parameter identifying incorrect or non-existent output data type - P_OF5 – "print" followed by "=" or other incorrect parameter 				
EVENTS				
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>				
EVENT 1 – C				
Student Id: 2810		Total of submissions of the exercise:		7
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
16	<pre>printf("%d %d %d" a, b, c);</pre>	16	<pre>printf("%d %d %d", a, b, c);</pre>	
Occurred in submission: 4		Fixed on submission: 5		
Observation:		Observation:		
EVENT 2 – C				
Student Id: 3167		Total of submissions of the exercise:		7
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1				
Error		Fixed Error		

<pre>7 printf ("%d%d%d" a1, a2, a3);</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<pre>7 printf ("%d%d%d", a1, a2, a3);</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3 – C	
Student Id: 5554	Total of submissions of the exercise: 4
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 7.4	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>13 printf ("%d\n" (int)c);</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>13 printf ("%d\n", c);</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4 – C	
Student Id: 2061	Total of submissions of the exercise: 2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 7.1	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>10 printf("%f" soma);</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>10 printf("%f", soma);</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 1 – Python	
Student Id: 4914	Total of submissions of the exercise: 11
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>print ("Sim" a, b, c) print ("NAO" a + b + c)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 5 Observation: Both "print" commands lack the required comma to separate the first from the second parameter.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>print ("Sim", a, b, c) print ("NAO", a + b + c)</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 6 Observation:</p>
EVENT 2 – Python	
Student Id: 4682	Total of submissions of the exercise: 3
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>print(a /n b /n c)</pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 1</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>print(a) print(b) print(c)</pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 2</p>

Observation: Missing comma to separate "print" parameters (Note: instead of "/" should be "\n" and need to be enclosed in double quotes (antipattern P_OF2))	Observation: Instead of adding commas to separate variables, it was separated into more "print."
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EVENT 3 – Python		
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Student Id: 5010	Total of submissions of the exercise:	4
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The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1		
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<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em;"> if (a+b+d==180): print("Sim" a b d) else: print("NAO" a+b+d) </pre> <p>Occurred in submission: 2 Observation: Both "print" lack comma to separate the first from the second parameter.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre style="font-family: monospace; font-size: 0.9em;"> if (a+b+d==180): print("Sim", a, b, d) else: print("NAO", a+b+d) </pre> <p>Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:</p>
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EVENT 4 – Python		
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Student Id:	Total of submissions of the exercise:	
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The exercise that was being solved:		
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<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <p>Occurred in submission: Observation:</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <p>Fixed on submission: Observation:</p>
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A SUGGESTED SOLUTION		
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FOR PROFESSORS		
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Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot		
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FOR STUDENTS		
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Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them		
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ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE					
RE1	Use of “=” instead of “==”					
EXAMPLES:						
(C)			(Python)			
9	<code>if(n1=n2)</code>		<code>if soma=180:</code>			
ERROR TYPE:	C (P)	Syntax	X (C)	Semantics		Style
CONTENT:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variable: attribution - Relational expression - Selection structure: if 					
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C		X	Python	
PROBLEM:						
<p><u>C</u> - Within parentheses after the "if" there should be a relational expression resulting in "True" or "False," but using only an equals sign "=" is attribution and not a comparison. For relational expressions, when you want to compare whether one value is equal to another, two equal signs together "==" are used.</p> <p><u>Python</u> - Equality check relational expressions use the "==" sign. Improper use of "=", which means assignment, where there should be "==" will cause the program not to run.</p>						
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:						
- V3 – Assignment using “==” instead of “=”						
EVENTS						
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>						
EVENT 1 – C						
Student Id: 1781		Total of submissions of the exercise:			7	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1						
Error 						
Occurred in submission: 4 Observation:			Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:			
EVENT 2 – C						
Student Id: 2950		Total of submissions of the exercise:			6	
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1						
Error 						

<p>Occurred in submission: 2 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 5 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3 – C	
<p>Student Id: 1830</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 4</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>5 if(a+b+c=180){</pre>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>5 if(a+b+c==180){</pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 4 – C	
<p>Student Id: 3300</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 4</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>13 if (soma = 180){</pre>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>13 if (soma == 180){</pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 4 Observation:</p>
EVENT 1 – Python	
<p>Student Id: 4850</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 15</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>if soma=180:</pre>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>if soma == 180:</pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 2 Observation: For comparison “==” and not “=” is used.</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 14 Observation:</p>
EVENT 2 – Python	
<p>Student Id: 4890</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 6</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Error</p> <pre>while d = 180:</pre>	<p style="text-align: center;">Fixed Error</p> <pre>while d == 180:</pre>
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:</p>	<p>Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:</p>
EVENT 3 – Python	
<p>Student Id: 4914</p>	<p>Total of submissions of the exercise: 11</p>
<p>The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1</p>	

Error	Fixed Error
<code>if a + b + c = 180:</code>	<code>if a + b + c == 180:</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
EVENT 4 – Python	
Student Id: 2558	Total of submissions of the exercise: 2
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.7	
Error	Fixed Error
<code>if a%2 = 1:</code>	<code>if a%2 == 1:</code>
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: 2 Observation:
A SUGGESTED SOLUTION	
FOR PROFESSORS	
Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot	
FOR STUDENTS	
Introduce the error into a code and understand the consequences it generates	

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE			
SS2	Not using "else" where it would be appropriate to do so			
EXAMPLES:				
(C)		(Python)		
<pre> 6 □ 7 8 9 □ 10 11 </pre>	<pre> if(a>b){ printf("%d",a); } if(b>a){ printf("%d",b); } </pre>	<pre> if i<j: print(j) if j<i: print(i) else: print(i) </pre>		
ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	Semantics	X	Style
CONTENT:	- Selection structure: if..else			
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	X	Python
PROBLEM:				
C and Python - The structure can give the expected result, but since only one of the selections can be true, the second would only need to be checked if the first were false.				
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:				
- P_SS1 – Missing “:” at end of “if” or “else” line				
EVENTS				
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>				
EVENT 1 – C				
Student Id: 1781		Total of submissions of the exercise:		7
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1				
Error		Fixed Error		
<pre> 6 □ 7 8 9 □ 10 11 </pre>	<pre> if(a>b){ printf("%d",a); } if(b>a){ printf("%d",b); } </pre>			
Occurred in submission: 2 Observation:		Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.		
EVENT 2 – C				
Student Id: 2040		Total of submissions of the exercise:		8
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 2.1				

Error	Fixed Error
<pre> 5 if(a>b) 6 { 7 printf(a); 8 } 9 if(b>a) 10 { 11 printf(b); 12 }</pre>	
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.

EVENT 3 – C

Student Id: 2061	Total of submissions of the exercise:	3
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The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.1

Error	Fixed Error
<pre> 5 if(a>b) printf("%d\n", a); 6 if(b>a) printf("%d\n", b); 7 if(a==b) printf("Iguais\n");</pre>	
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.

EVENT 4 – C

Student Id: 5730	Total of submissions of the exercise:	6
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The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 3.1

Error	Fixed Error
<pre> 4 if (a+b+c==180){ 5 printf("sim"); 6 printf("%d %d %d", a, b, c); 7 } 8 if (a+b+c!=180){ 9 printf("nao"); 10 printf("%d %d %d", a, b, c); 11 } 12 </pre>	
Occurred in submission: 1 Observation:	Fixed on submission: Observation: The error has not been fixed.

EVENT 1 – Python

Student Id: 4674	Total of submissions of the exercise:	7
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The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.1

Error	Fixed Error
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Attempt 1:

```

if i<j:
    print(j)
if j<i:
    print(i)
else:
    print(i)

```

Occurred in submission: 4
Observation: As the above selection structure was set up, before the second "if" an "else" is required.

```

if i<j:
    print(j)
if j<i:
    print(i)

Final:
if i<j:
    print(j)
else:
    print(i)

```

Fixed on submission: 6
Observation:

EVENT 2 – Python

Student Id: 4730 **Total of submissions of the exercise: 7**

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.1

Error

```

if(x>y):
    print("O maior numero e", x)
if(x<y):
    print("O maior numero e", y)

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```

if x > y:
    print("O maior numero e", x)
else:
    print("O maior numero e", y)

```

Fixed on submission: 6
Observation:

EVENT 3 – Python

Student Id: 4794 **Total of submissions of the exercise: 3**

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.1

Error

```

if x > n:
    print(x)
if n > x
    print(n)

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

Fixed Error

```

if x > n:
    print(x)
else:
    print(n)

```

Fixed on submission: 3
Observation:

EVENT 4 – Python

Student Id: 4826 **Total of submissions of the exercise: 21**

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 2.1

Error

Fixed Error

```
if m > n:
    print (m)
if m < n:
    print (n)
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation:

```
if m > n:
    print (m)
else:
    print (n)
```

Fixed on submission: 2
Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION FOR PROFESSORS

Apply the bench test (table test) in code samples with and without the error, compare the results – reinforce by asking the students to solve some exercises

FOR STUDENTS

Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

ANTI-PATTERN GENERAL DATA

ID	TITLE																						
RS2	Control variable is not change																						
EXAMPLES:																							
(C)			(Python)																				
<pre>14 15 </pre>	<pre>while (aux < 3) printf("SIM %d %d %d", a, b, c);</pre>	<pre>while (i<=n): print ord(c[i])</pre>																					
<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%;">ERROR TYPE:</td> <td style="width: 16.5%;">Syntax</td> <td style="width: 16.5%; text-align: center;">X</td> <td style="width: 16.5%;">Semantics</td> <td style="width: 16.5%;"></td> <td style="width: 16.5%;">Style</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CONTENT:</td> <td colspan="5" style="text-align: center;">- Repetition structure: while</td> </tr> <tr> <td>IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?</td> <td style="text-align: center;">X</td> <td style="text-align: center;">C</td> <td style="text-align: center;">X</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Python</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>						ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics		Style	CONTENT:	- Repetition structure: while					IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	X	Python	
ERROR TYPE:	Syntax	X	Semantics		Style																		
CONTENT:	- Repetition structure: while																						
IN WHAT LANGUAGE WAS THE MISTAKE MADE?	X	C	X	Python																			
PROBLEM:																							
<p><u>C and Python</u>: The program will go into an infinite loop because, since the control variable is never changed, the result of the condition that controls the repetition will not change either.</p>																							
CONNECTIONS TO OTHER ANTI-PATTERNS:																							
EVENTS																							
<p>Note: In the code snippets presented below, only the anti-pattern question of this table was analyzed. If other errors exist, these errors have been handled in other anti-patterns.</p>																							
EVENT 1 – C																							
Student Id: 3300		Total of submissions of the exercise:			4																		
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 3.1																							
Error			Fixed Error																				
<pre>14 15 </pre>	<pre>while (aux < 3) printf("SIM %d %d %d", a, b, c);</pre>	<pre>14 15 16 17 </pre>	<pre>while (aux < 3){ printf("SIM %d %d %d", a, b, c); aux++; }</pre>																				
<p>Occurred in submission: 1 Observation: The control variable “aux” was initialized to 0 (zero) but did not change its value within the “while,” generating infinite repetitions.</p>			<p>Fixed on submission: 3 Observation: Error fixed by adding the increment in line 16.</p>																				
EVENT 2 – C																							
Student Id: 1781		Total of submissions of the exercise:			12																		
The exercise that was being solved: Exercise 4.7																							
Error			Fixed Error																				

```

9
10
11
12
13

```

```

while(a!=0)
{
    b=b+a;
    printf("%d",b);
}

```


Occurred in submission: 1
Observation: It will go into infinite repetition because of control variable "a" is not changing its value.

Fixed on submission:
Observation: The error has not been fixed.

EVENT 3 – C

Student Id: 4770 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 3

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 4.7

Error

```

6
7
8
9
10
11

```

```

scanf("%d", &j);
while(j != 0){
    if((j % 2) != 0){
        soma += j;
    }
}

```

Occurred in submission: 2
Observation: Control variable "j" is initialized (line 6), compared (line 7), but has not changed its value, which should happen between lines 10 and 11.

Fixed Error

```

6
7
8
9
10
11
12

```

```

scanf("%d", &j);
while(j != 0){
    if((j % 2) != 0){
        soma += j;
    }
    scanf("%d", &j);
}

```

Fixed on submission: 3
Observation:

EVENT 4 – C

Student Id: 1963 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 21

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 8.1

Error

```

3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11

```

```

int determineSeOrdenado(int n, int vet[]) {
    int i = 0;
    while (i < n) {
        if (vet[i] <= vet [i+1]) {
        } else {
            return 0;
            break;
        }
    }
}

```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation: The control variable "i" of "while" did not change its value within the repetition.

Fixed Error

```

3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11

```

```

int determineSeOrdenado(int n, int vet[]) {
    int i = 0;
    while (i < n) {
        if (vet[i] > vet [i+1]) {
            return 0;
            break;
        }
        i++;
    }
}

```

Fixed on submission: 4
Observation:

EVENT 1 – Python

Student Id: 3498 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 5

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 7.4

Error

Fixed Error

```
i=1
while(i<=n):
    print ord(c[i])
```

Occurred in submission: 2
Observation: Control variable "i" is not change within "while," causing infinite repetitions.

```
i=1
while(i<=n):
    print ord(c[i])
    i=i+1
```

Fixed on submission: 3
Observation:

EVENT 2 – Python

Student Id: 4690 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 16

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 7.4

Error

```
n = int(input())
l = []
while n > 0:
    c = raw_input()
    l.append(c)
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation: Control variable "n" is not changing within "while," causing infinite repetition.

Fixed Error

```
n = int(input())
l = []
c = raw_input()
while n > 0:
    l.append(c)
    n = n - 1
```

Fixed on submission: 3
Observation:

EVENT 3 – Python

Student Id: 4730 **Total of submissions of the exercise:** 9

The exercise that was being solved:
Exercise 7.4

Error

```
n = int(input("Digite um numero: "))
c = raw_input("Digite uma palavra com", n, " caracteres")
x = 0
while n!=0:
    print(c.chr(x))
    x = x-1
```

Occurred in submission: 1
Observation: Disregarding other errors and looking at the "while" repetition structure, the control variable "n" is not changing, causing infinite repetition.

Fixed Error

```
n = int(input("Digite um numero: "))
while n>0:
    c = raw_input("Digite os caracteres: ")
    print(ord(c))
    n = n-1
```

Fixed on submission: 9
Observation:

EVENT 4 – Python

Student Id: **Total of submissions of the exercise:**

The exercise that was being solved:

Error

Occurred in submission:
Observation:

Fixed Error

Fixed on submission:
Observation:

A SUGGESTED SOLUTION

FOR PROFESSORS

Apply the bench test (table test) in code samples with and without the error, compare the results – reinforce by asking the students to solve some exercises

FOR STUDENTS

Introduce the error into a code and understand the consequences it generates